

ПРОГНОСТИЧНА ЦІННІСТЬ ІНДЕКСУ ФУНКЦІОНАЛЬНОЇ ЗДАТНОСТІ МІОКАРДА У ПАЦІЄНТІВ З ГІПЕРТИРЕОЗОМ

THE PROGNOSTIC VALUE OF MYOCARDIAL PERFORMANCE INDEX IN PATIENTS WITH HYPERTHYROIDISM

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Introduction. Hyperthyroidism has been identified as an important cardiovascular risk factor (1). Excess thyroid hormones reduce myocardial reserve capacity and lead to left ventricular systolic dysfunction (2). Also, there is diastolic dysfunction as a result of impaired myocardial relaxation (3).

Early echocardiography (EchoCG) may be of great value in diagnosing subclinical heart failure in patients with hyperthyroidism (4). The Tei index, also known as the myocardial performance index (MPI), which is capable of globally assessing systolic and diastolic heart function, can provide important prognostic information in such patients (5).

The aim of this study is to evaluate the prognostic value of the MPI in predicting subclinical heart failure in hyperthyroid patients.

Materials and methods. 78 participants were enrolled in the study: 40 patients with newly diagnosed hyperthyroidism - the 1st group (30 female, 10 males; mean age 42,4 ± 13,7 years) and 38 healthy persons without known medical conditions as a control - the 2nd group (27 female, 11 males; 46,6 ± 15,6 years).

Exclusion criteria were: any evidence of cardiovascular diseases, high blood pressure, and use of chronic prescription medications. Thyroid hormone profile (T3free, T4free, and TSH) assessment was made for all participants of the study.

Standard EchoCG was performed using SonoScape S6Pro ultrasound. Basal measurements were performed with M-mode in the parasternal long-axis view. The function of the left ventricle was determined using tissue Doppler examination by measurement of ejection time (ET), isovolumetric contraction time (IVCT), and isovolumetric relaxation time (IVRT). The MPI was calculated by dividing the sum of IVCT and IVRT by ET.

Data were analyzed using one-factor analysis ANOVA.

Results. Analysis of the profile of thyroid hormones shows a significantly lower average level of TSH and an increased average level of T3free, and T4free in the 1st group compared to the 2nd group ($p=0.018$, $p<0,001$ and $p=0,02$; respectively).

Each study participant was measured IVCT, IVRT, ET, MPI, and ejection fraction (EF) using EchoCG, and the results of both groups were compared with each other.

IVCT was significantly higher in the 1st group than control participants ($0,05 \pm 0,015$ vs $0,039 \pm 0,008$; $p=0,032$). Conversely, IVRT showed no significant difference between subjects with and without hyperthyroidism ($0,075 \pm 0,025$ vs $0,079 \pm 0,012$; $p=0,599$). Average values of the ET in the group 1 were lower than that in the group 2 ($0,27 \pm 0,036$ vs $0,34 \pm 0,028$; $p<0,001$).

Patients with hyperthyroidism showed significantly higher MPI for the left ventricle as compared to healthy patients ($0,48 \pm 0,15$ vs $0,35 \pm 0,08$; $p=0,009$). The EF was within the normal range in both groups and there were no significant differences in it between the two studied groups ($67,58 \pm 3,37$ vs $67,2 \pm 4,82$; $p=0,413$).

Conclusion. The study showed that the regression of the left ventricle function is an important prognostic echocardiographic feature in hyperthyroid patients. MPI has proven to be a sensitive and useful tool for diagnosing subclinical systolic and diastolic left ventricular dysfunction in these patients.

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